

ISic2786

I.Sicily inscription 2786

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (local stone, from Fuardo)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Contr. Diana, sporadic find

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 13848

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ελλ[---]

Apparatus

Meligunìs Lipára XII

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645183

PHI 334258

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 45.1381.22

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le

iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 156
Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M. 1994. Meligunis Lipara VII. Lipari. Contrada
Diana. Scavo XXXVI in proprieta Zagami (1975-1984). Palermo. At no.22 pl.125

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic2786. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI
edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4355158>